

Deliverable: 2.3: I-ENERGY Components, Services & Architecture (first version)

30th MAY 2022

Lead: ENG

Version: 1.0

Classification: Public

www.i-energy.eu

I-ENERGY project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016508

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2020 Research and Innovation
programme under grant agreement
No 101016508

I-ENERGY Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.:	101016508
Acronym:	I-ENERGY
Title:	Artificial Intelligence for Next Generation Energy
Type:	Innovation Action (IA)
URL:	https://i-nergy.eu/
Start Date:	01/01/2021
Duration:	36 months

Work Package:	WP2 – Requirements, Specifications, Synergies and Alignment with AI4EU
Deliverable Leader:	ENG
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Internal Reviewers:	Spiros Mouzakis (ICCS), Antonis Psychas (ICCS)
Status:	Final
Date of Delivery:	30th MAy 2022
Version:	2.00
Classification:	Public

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.10	09/06/2021	Giampaolo Fiorentino (ENG)	ToC
0.53	14/06/2021	Giampaolo Fiorentino (ENG)	Reviewed ToC
0.54	06/08/2021	Leandro Lombardo (ENG)	First version of section 6.2 , 6.2.1, 6.2.2, 6.2.3
0.6	06/08/2021	Giampaolo Fiorentino (ENG)	4.1,4.2,4.3, 5, 6.2.5
0.61	16/9/2021	Vagelis Karakolis (ICCS), Spiros Mouzakis (ICCS), Sotiris Pelekis (ICCS), George Korbakis (ICCS), George Lampropoulos (ICCS)	Section 6.1 – new architecture diagram, section 6.4
0.62	20/09/2021	Chijioko Eze (RWTH)	6.3
0.63	20/09/2021	Charles Emehel (RWTH)	First version of 5.3
1.0	05/10/2021	Spiros Mouzakis (ICCS)	Quality Check and Final version
1.2	15/01/2022	Giampaolo Fiorentino (ENG)	Structure refinement for new resubmission
1.6	10/02/2022	Giampaolo Fiorentino (ENG), Spiros Mouzakis (ICCS), Charles Emehel (RWTH)	Contributions to address remarks
1.7	24/04/2022	Carolina Fortuna (COMS)	Add the last Contribution
1.8	03/05/2022	Giampaolo Fiorentino(ENG)	First version
2.0	23/05/2022	Spiros Mouzakis (ICCS)	Quality Check and Final version

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15	VEOLIA SERVICIOS LECAM SOCIEDAD ANONIMA UNIPERSONAL	VEOLIA	ES	
16	RIGA MUNICIPAL AGENCY "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"	REA	LV	
17	FUNDACION ASTURIANA DE LA ENERGIA	FAEN	ES	

Abbreviations

Term	Definition	Term	Definition	Term	Definition
AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation	EFI	Energy Flexibility Interface	PaaS	Platform as a Service
API	Application Programming Interface	ENEF	Energy Efficiency	PMUs	Phasor Measurement Units
AI	Artificial Intelligence	ESCO	Energy Service Companies	PV	Photovoltaic
AlaaS	Al-as-a-Service	EPES	Electric Power & Energy Systems	P2P	Peer-to-peer
B2B	Business to Business	EU	European Union	RES	Renewable Energy Sources
BDA	Big Data Analytic	EV	Electric Vehicle	RoI	Return of Investment
BDVA/DAIRO	Big Data Value Association/ Data, AI and Robotics	FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties	RTD	Research and Tech. Development
COSMAG	Comprehensive Archit. For Smart Grid	GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	SAREF	Smart Appliances REFerence ontol.
DaaS	Data-as-Service	IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service	SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture
DER	Distributed Energy Resource	ICT	Information and Control Technologies	SIMaaS	Simulation-as-a-Service
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs	IEDs	Intelligent Electronic Devices	SCADA	Supervisory/Control/Data Acquisition
DL	Deep Learning	IA	Innovation Action	SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
DLT	Distributed ledger technology	IoT	Internet of Things	SNET	Smart Networks Energy Transition
DSM	Digital Single Market	IFIs	International Financial Institutions	TTP	Technology Transfer Programme
DSO	Distribution Service Operator	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
DSS	Decision Support System	KPI	Key Performance Indicator	TSO	Transmission system operator
EC	European Commission	ML	Machine Learning	WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

This document is organized as follows. Chapter 2 reports the approach for collecting, analysing and leveraging existing architecture efforts. Chapter 3 presents the needs and main requirement of I-ENERGY platform. Chapter 4 describes the relevant architecture models and puts them into the context of I-ENERGY and WP2 efforts, and Chapter 5 discusses established data space Architectures and their possible integration with I-ENERGY. Subsequently, Chapter 6 builds upon these chapters to converge the discussed efforts into a first version of the I-ENERGY Conceptual Architecture.

2 Overview of I-ENERGY Reference Architecture Approach

This section enumerates existing reference architectures to consider toward the specification of the I-ENERGY reference architecture. Additionally, it gives a perspective on which aspects to consider for I-ENERGY reference architecture alignment with the LSPs.

The reference architecture efforts can be divided coarsely into four groups: architecture models, project coalitions, data space reference architectures, and microservice architectures. These groups are explained in more detail in the next subsections.

The architecture models are BRIDGE, COSMAG, and RAMI. For project coalitions, OPEN DEI, BDVA/DAIRO, and AIOTI are considered. Furthermore, the data space reference architectures IDS/GAIA-X, FIWARE, and the AIOTI Marketplace are examined. SOGNO and other Linux Foundation Energy (LFE) projects serve as examples of concrete microservice architectures.

The objective in aligning these efforts is not only to capture the data exchange requirements such as interoperability, sovereignty, trust and security of I-ENERGY use cases, but also to provide a flexible and general, yet sufficiently detailed reference architecture as a guideline for subsequent implementation and integration with AI4EU platform. At the same time, I-ENERGY is aiming at representing a first-of-this-kind validation of IDSA conceptual architecture along the energy domain, hence providing significant contribution to the parallel work currently being carried out within the Energy Working Group of GAIA-X. To these ends and to promote acceptance, emphasis is to be put on building it following eminent architectural models, mainly BRIDGE which in turn extends SGAM. Furthermore, evaluating maturity and identifying reusable building blocks from the more concrete data space reference architectures, particularly GAIA-X/IDS and FIWARE is paramount for the most efficient use of resources possible.

3 I-ENERGY platform: Needs and constraints.

This section identifies the technical constraints and specifications in a draft way, as well as the desired functionalities and usage of the platform to be designed.

3.1 AI-on-demand Energy Services Specifications

In Task 2.1 the analysis of pilots creating user stories and requirement took place and the first list of services were identified to be developed in WP3 and WP4. Then, the services were mapped to the I-ENERGY domains: I-NET, I-DER and I-ENEF, as shown in Figure 1. Finally, in T2.4 (D2.4), the alignment of I-ENERGY and AI4EU services was done. This step was done to find synergies and existing material produced by the AI4EU projects that can contribute or be used by the I-ENERGY services.

The list of Services (labelled with S and the corresponding number) are:

- S1: Visual analytics dashboard for electricity consumption centers
- S2: Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
- S3: Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
- S4: Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation
- S5: Climate change solar radiation forecasting
- S6: Digital Twin: DER simulation for supporting system level scenario evaluation
- S7: Predictive Maintenance Analytics
- S8: Measurement and verification of energy savings
- S9: Energy flexibility forecasting
- S10: Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting
- S11: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation
- S12: Optimization of the production mix
- S13: I-ENERGY Virtual Workbench - Marketplace (catalogue of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application)
- S14: Activity recognition and forecasting
- S15: Anomalous behaviour detection
- S16: Blockchain Hybrid energy data storage

Three Services S1, S13 and S16, are the general services that are not linked to the I-ENERGY domains. The services can be span over tree deployment mode:

- > AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS), in this domain, are most of the services, all AI analytical services, visual service (S1) and I-ENERGY Digital twins energy services (S2, S6) Platform as a Service (Paas), is a virtual workbench that supports the selection, reuse, reconfiguration of trained models through the I-ENERGY model library and is covered by the S13 service.
- > Infrastructure as a service (IaaS), is based on distributed applications, providing data and processing tasks as virtualised components that can be flexibly managed over a decentralised cloud architecture. The platform will package its services, as an adapted open source sandbox, in container-based workflows that could be flexibly deployed over cloud infrastructures through a service orchestrator.

Figure 1: Mapping of services to I-ENERGY domains

3.2 AI-related Ethical Guidelines and Recommendations

The overall I-ENERGY framework, including the I-ENERGY platform, adheres to all legal and ethical frameworks that are applicable within I-ENERGY project. Towards this commitment, a dedicated Deliverable (D2.2) is prepared, providing a) an overview of the applicable legislative frameworks within I-ENERGY project and energy domain considering EU and international legislation, b) an analysis of possible implications and ethical issues that may arise from the adoption of AI in the energy domain, c) an analysis of the principles and the requirements for ethical AI and d) a set of guidelines concerning the handling of IPR within I-ENERGY.

I-ENERGY’s approach to the regulatory framework is based on the dimensions of a) privacy and data protection, b) network and information security and c) energy domain policy and standards. All the components involved in the I-ENERGY technical solution should ensure the protection of privacy and individuals’ rights as well as the protection of the data. The data protection concerns the whole lifecycle of the data, including among others, collection, storage and processing. The D2.2 analysis of the data protection frameworks focuses, without being limited, on the GDPR. The network and information security dimension of the deliverable focuses on the NIS Directive and aims to spread a common understanding of the NIS Directive and its adoption through the whole project’s lifecycle and especially during the design and development steps, providing an analysis of its main requirements and guidelines. The analysis concerning the energy domain policy and standards, provides an overview of some key initiatives and organizations, raising awareness and providing guidance for the I-ENERGY services and the context of their application.

I-ENERGY’s approach to the Ethics of AI contains an analysis of common ethical issues that may arise from the adoption of AI focusing on those in the energy domain. In addition, D2.2 provides an overview of the principles and requirements that AI systems, and therefore the I-ENERGY AI-based applications, should respect towards trustworthy AI. This overview is based on the relevant effort of AI HLEG about “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”.

The IPR related guidelines reported within D2.2 aim to raise awareness regarding the management of IPR issues and how they are addressed within the I-ENERGY project and Consortium.

4 Architecture Models

4.1 COSMAG

COSMAG (Comprehensive Architecture for Smart Grid) is an effort to define specifications for any possible data-exchange interaction in the Smart Energy sector, with the aim of helping the transition of the energy system to a Data Economy, addressing the key issues related to the needs for a Digital Single Market within Europe.

COSMAG does not aim to define any new standard and is instead based on existing efforts and architectures. Among these are the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM)¹ and the work by EC Smart Grids Task Force – Expert Group 3².

SGAM is a three-dimensional model, represented by Figure 2, that comprises five interoperability layers (Business, Function, Information, Communication and Component), as well as a Smart Grid plane with two dimensions: Zones, representing the hierarchical level of the power system (Process, Field, Station, Operation, Enterprise, Market) and Domains, depicting the electrical energy conversion chain (Generation, Transmission, Distribution, DER, Customer Premises).

Figure 2: The Smart Grid Architecture Model.

Figure 3 depicts the possible roles, market interactions and actors that are envisioned as part of a modern electricity market in the SGTF – EG3 Report.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/xpert_group1_reference_architecture.pdf

² Regulatory Recommendations for the Deployment of Flexibility (<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/EG3%20Final%20-%20January%202015.pdf>)

Figure 3: Possible roles, market interactions and actors envisioned in the SGTF – EG3 Report.

This representation allows an analysis of the most important communication flows and their maturity, considering both the status of the protocol definitions and data models.

The list of actors derived from the Figure 3 is not exhaustive. Other actors could be identified, some of which are listed below. Interfaces with local markets have not been defined as there is no existing local market up to date, but COSMAG allows to consider its future presence.

TSO

- TSO – Market (balancing)
- TSO – DSO

DSO

- DSO – Local Market (no local markets yet)
- DSO – Prosumer

AGGREGATOR

- Aggregator – Local Market (no local markets yet)
- Aggregator – DSO (integration of network constraints)
- Aggregator – Prosumer (e.g. OpenADR)

PROSUMER

- Prosumer – Retail (mainly metering, e.g. DLMS/COSEM)
- Prosumer – Prosumer (local energy communities)

A defining goal of COSMAG is sector coupling. More specifically, achieving cross-sector and cross-stakeholder data exchange through common standards regarding data models and ontologies, comprehensive documentation and Open APIs. Additionally, the use of DLTs for secure and trusted data share among stakeholders and exploitation of Big Data by avoiding the creation of data silos will allow links to other platforms, like those related to smart cities, heating, transportation, building technologies, industries, etc.

4.2 BRIDGE Reference Architecture

BRIDGE is an initiative of the European Commission where 64 Horizon 2020 projects, in the context of Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation, are involved to pool field experience, feedback, and lessons learned, to create a structured view of cross-cutting issues that are encountered in the demonstration projects to help overcome the barriers to effective innovation.

In that sense, BRIDGE aims at providing coordinated and coherent recommendations to strengthen the messages and maximize their impacts towards policy makers.

The BRIDGE initiative fosters continuous knowledge sharing amongst projects with the aim to deliver, in a single voice, conclusions and recommendations about the exploitation of results from the different projects through four different Working Groups representing the main areas of interest:

- Data management
- Business models
- Regulations
- Consumer and Citizen engagement.

Within BRIDGE Working Groups, the Working Group on Data Management is the most relevant for the work related to the I-ENERGY RA. It is working on:

- Communication Infrastructure, embracing the technical and non-technical aspects of the communication infrastructure needed to exchange data and the related requirements, including issues faced by TSO and DSO.
- Cybersecurity and Data Privacy, entailing data integrity, customer privacy and protection.
- Data Handling, including the framework for data exchange and related roles and responsibilities, together with the technical issues supporting the exchange of data in a secure and interoperable manner, and the data analytics techniques for data processing.

After the 2019 BRIDGE General Assembly, Task Forces have been launched to work on specific topics, such as Energy Communities, Replicability / Scalability Analysis, Joint Communication and R&I Priorities.

Horizon2020 smart grid projects under the umbrella of BRIDGE Initiative have investigated the usage of Data Exchange platforms and interoperability of those platforms to define recommendations for a business process agnostic data exchange reference architecture in the energy domain. The results of this activity expect to facilitate cross-sector and cross-border data exchange at European level, ensuring free flow of data among stakeholders, while ensuring GDPR compliance and data owner's control over their data. In view of this, the BRIDGE initiative has analysed eleven other R&D projects by gathering general information on the projects through surveys and requesting specific information on organisational, informational, and technical aspects of the projects. A subsequent mapping of results to the smart grid architecture model (SGAM)³ interoperability layers results in the BRIDGE RA. These layers are:

- Business Layer, which represents the business view on the information exchange related to smart grids.
- Function Layer, which describes functions and services including their relationships from an architectural viewpoint.
- Information Layer, which describes the information that is being used and exchanged between functions, services and components. It contains information objects and the underlying canonical data models. that represent the common semantics for functions and services to allow an interoperable information exchange via communication means.
- Communication Layer, which describe protocols and mechanisms for the interoperable exchange of information between components in the context of the underlying use case, function or service and related information objects or data models.
- Component Layer, which includes system actors, applications, power system equipment, protection and tele-control devices, network infrastructure (wired / wireless communication connections, routers, switches, servers), and any kind of computers.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/xpert_group1_reference_architecture.pdf

BRIDGE is looking only at one of the three dimensions of SGAM, the dimension of the five layers above described, sometimes called interoperability layer, as shown in the BRIDGE Reference Architecture⁴ in Figure 4. The top part of the architecture shows the other scales: electricity domain on the left, other domains (gas, water, transport, health, etc) on the right side, and cross-sector in the middle.

The idea is to bring together the input from individual domains (mainly electricity but also other domains). In the cross-sector domain section, the commonalities of the different domains, essentially related to the data management, are placed. The energy sector is comprised of multiple vectors, mainly electricity, natural gas and district heating utilities. The possible cross-vector integration within the energy sector is being considered by the BRIDGE initiative. In view of this, dependencies among the vectors in the energy sector, due to seasonality and variability effects, need to be taken into consideration.

As depicted in Figure 4, each of the interoperability layers has been divided into sub-layers and for each sub-layer some examples are provided.

The Business Layer is split into:

- Regulation
- Associations
- Business Roles
- Business Processes

The Function Layer includes functional processes, such as grid modelling, flexibility management.

The Information Layer is split into:

- Information Models, ontologies
- Profiles, data models.

The Communication Layer is split into:

- Data Formats
- Protocols

The Component Layer is split into:

- Data exchange platforms
- Applications
- Hardware.

On the right side of the architecture, there are recommendations provided for each layer and sub-layer. Data source integration is the key feature of the utilities; thus, it is essential to identify interdependencies and data exchange flows among these utilities. Moreover, the architecture integrates other sectors (gas, heating, water, etc.).

⁴https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/default/files/documents/bridge_wg_data_management_eu_reference_architecture_report_2020-2021.pdf

Figure 4: The BRIDGE Reference Architecture

From the architecture models presented in this document the BRIDGE RA offers the most complete view of use cases in the electricity sector as well as cross-sectorial use cases. It extends the widely accepted SGAM. This makes it a suitable model for expressing the I-ENERGY.

4.3 International Data Spaces (IDS)⁵

The International Data Spaces initiative has defined a Reference Architecture Model (RAM) to ensure Data Sovereignty, including requirements for secure and trusted data exchange in business ecosystems.

The architecture is designed with the objective to overcome the differences between top-down approaches and bottom-up approaches. Figure 5 shows a typical architecture stack of the digital industrial enterprise.

⁵ IDS Reference Architecture Model 3.0 (<https://internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/IDS-RAM-3.0-2019.pdf>)

Figure 5: IDS RAM 3.0: Typical enterprise architecture stack

The IDS connects the lower-level architectures for communication and basic data services with more abstract architectures for smart data services. It therefore supports the establishment of secure data supply chains from data source to data use, while at the same time making sure data sovereignty is guaranteed for data owners.

As depicted in Figure 6, the IDS RAM is made up of five layers and three perspectives that need to be implemented across the five layers.

Figure 6: IDS RAM Layers and Perspectives.

The IDS Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) provides several elements, roles and interactions that constitute an infrastructure for sovereign data exchange (see Figure 7). There are four categories of roles:

- Category 1: Core Participant
- Category 2: Intermediary
- Category 3: Software / Service Provider
- Category 4: Governance Body

The Core Participants are Data Owner, Data Provider, Data Consumer and Data User. They are involved and required every time data is exchanged in the IDS. Intermediaries act as trusted entities. These are the Broker Service provider, an intermediary that stores and manages information about the data sources available in the IDS; the Clearing House, that provides clearing and settlement services for all financial and data exchange transactions; and the Identity Provider, which consists of a Certification Authority (managing digital certificates for the participants of the IDS), a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS, managing the dynamic attributes of the participants), and a service named Dynamic Trust Monitoring (DTM, for continuous monitoring of

the security and behaviour of the network. The 3rd category comprises IT companies providing software and/or services (e.g., based on a software-as-a-service model) to the participants of the IDS. The Certification Body, Evaluation Facilities, and the International Data Spaces Association are the Governance Bodies of the International Data Spaces.

Figure 7: IDS Roles and Interactions

The IDS connector is the core component of the IDS RAM as it is the access to a trusted ecosystem. It is responsible for the data exchange. In an IDS ecosystem, the data is transferred between the Connectors of the Data Provider and the Data Consumer (peer-to-peer network concept).

4.3.1 IDS Data Governance Model

Data Governance is a fundamental element in the International Data Spaces ecosystem, since it acts as an enabler for successfully engaging in a collaborative ecosystem. As depicted in Figure 6, Data Governance is one of the three perspectives of the IDS Reference Architecture Model.

The IDS-RAM distributes decision rights for data governance and management activities to the different roles in the International Data Spaces ecosystem. It thereby supports the requirements to be met by the actors within the ecosystem to achieve secure and reliable interoperability as well as as desirable behaviour regarding the use of data.

The IDS Data Governance Model defines a framework of decision-making rights and processes with regards to the definition, creation, processing, and use of data. While governance activities set the overall directive of the decision-making system, data management comprises three groups of activities with regards to the creation, processing, and use of data. In the IDS context, data governance comprises also usage rights of data shared and exchanged within the IDS ecosystem. The management of metadata specifies data about data and comprises both syntactical, semantic and pragmatic information.

This is of particular importance in distributed system environments that do not rely on a central instance for data storage, but instead allow self-organization of different heterogeneous databases. Additionally, data lifecycle management is concerned with the creation and capturing of data, including data processing, enrichment, storage, distribution, and use.

The following responsibility assignment matrix (RACI matrix, see Table 1) supports the allocation of these activities to enable a governance mechanism in the IDS ecosystem. RACI stands for

“responsible”, “accountable”, “consulted” and “informed”. The focus lies on the „R” and „A” of the RACI matrix, supported by the notation „S”, which stands for „supported”.

Activity	Data Owner / Data Provider	Data User / Data Consumer	Broker	Clearing House
Management				
Determine data usage restrictions (execute data ownership rights)	R, A	-	S	-
Enforce data usage restrictions	-	R, A	-	-
Ensure data quality	R, A	-	S	-
Monitor and log data transactions	S	S	-	R, A
Enable data provenance	S	S	-	R, A
Provide clearing services	S	S	-	R, A
Metadata				
Describe and publish metadata	R, A	-	S	-
Look up and retrieve metadata	-	R, A	S	-
Data Lifecycle				
Capture and create data	R, A	-	-	-
Store data	R, A	S	-	-
Enrich and aggregate data	S	R, A	S	-
Distribute and provide data	R, A	-	S	-
Link data	S	S	R, A	-

Legend: R – Responsible; A – Accountable; S – Supporting.

Table 1: Roles responsible, accountable and supporting in data governance.

4.3.2 GAIA-X⁶

4.3.2.1 GAIA-X Architecture Overview

The GAIA-X project was started in 2019 with the aim to enable a secure, open and sovereign use of data. It is motivated by challenges to the European digital economy, such as:

- › Decentralised processing locations
- › Lack of transparency and sovereignty over stored and processed data and infrastructure
- › Sector-specific data spaces and lack of ontology

As shown in Figure 8, the GAIA-X reference architecture comprises an infrastructure ecosystem, where infrastructure services are provided, connected or consumed, and a data ecosystem, that

⁶ GAIA-X: Technical Architecture (https://www.datainfrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Redaktion/EN/Publications/gaia-x-technical-architecture.pdf?_blob=publicationFile&v=5)

deals with data as the main business asset. Both ecosystems are connected via the federation services. They include Identity and Trust Services, Compliance Services, Federated Catalogues and Sovereign Data Exchange Services.

This architecture serves as an underlying framework common to all domains.

Figure 8: GAIA-X Architecture

To ensure high-level data protection, security, transparency and portability within the GAIA-X ecosystem, a framework of Policy Rules is being developed.

GAIA-X defines three main roles which a participant can take on:

- > Provider: Provides Assets and Resources in the GAIA-X Ecosystem.
- > Consumer: Searches for Service Offerings and consumes Service Instances in the GAIA-X Ecosystem to enable digital offerings for End-Users.
- > Federator: Federators oversee the Federation Services and the Federation which are autonomous of each other.

4.3.2.2 Data Sovereignty Services

Data Sovereignty Services provide Participants the capability to be entirely self-determined regarding the exchange and sharing of their data. They can also decide to act without having the Data Sovereignty Service involved if they wish to do so.

Informational self-determination for all Participants comprises two aspects within the Data Ecosystem: Transparency of data usages and control of data usages. Enabling Data Sovereignty when exchanging, sharing and using data relies on fundamental functions and capabilities that are provided by Federation Services in conjunction with other mechanisms, concepts, and standards. The Data Sovereignty Services build on existing concepts of usage control that extends traditional access control. Thus, usage control is concerned with requirements that pertain to future data usages (i.e., obligations), rather than data access (provisions).

Capabilities for Data Sovereignty Services

The foundation for Data Sovereignty is a trust-management mechanism to enable a reliable foundation for peer-to-peer data exchange and usage, but also to enable data value chains with multiple Providers and Consumers being involved. All functions and capabilities can be extended and configured based on domain-specific or use case-specific requirements to form reusable schemes.

The following capabilities are essential for Data Sovereignty in the GAIA-X Data Ecosystems:

Capability	Description
Expression of Policies in a machine-readable form	To enable transparency and control of data usages, it is important to have a common policy specification language to express data usage restrictions in a formal and technology-independent manner that is agreed and understood by all Gaia-X Participants. Therefore, they have to be formalized and expressed in a common standard such as ODRL ¹³ .
Inclusion of Policies in Self-Description	Informational self-determination and transparency require metadata to describe Data Assets including Provider, Consumer, and Usage Policies as provided by Self-Descriptions and the Federated Catalogues.
Interpretation of Usage Policies	For a Policy to be agreed upon, it must be understood by all Participants in a way that enables negotiation and possible technical and organizational enforcement of Policies.
Enforcement	Monitoring of data usage is a detective enforcement of data usage with subsequent (compensating) actions. In contrast, preventive enforcement ¹⁴ ensures the policy Compliance with technical means (e.g., cancel or modify data flows).

Table 2: Capabilities for GAIA-X Data Sovereignty Services

Functions of Data Sovereignty Services

Information services provide more detailed information about the general context of the data usage transactions. All information on the data exchange and data usage transactions must be traceable; therefore, agreed monitoring and logging capabilities are required for all data usage transactions. Self-determination also means that Providers can choose to apply no Usage Policies at all.

The Data Sovereignty Services in GAIA-X implement different functions for different phases of the data exchanges. Therefore, three phases of data exchanges must be differentiated:

- > before transaction
- > during transaction
- > after transaction

The services are depicted in Figure 9.

Before the data exchange transaction, the Data Agreement Service is triggered and both parties negotiate a data exchange agreement. This includes Usage Policies and the required measures to implement those.

During transactions, a Data Logging Service receives logging-messages that are useful to trace each transaction. This includes data provided, data received, policy enforced, and policy-violating messages.

During and after the transaction the information stored can be queried by the transaction partners and a third eligible party, if required. The figure below shows the role of mentioned services to enable sovereign data exchange.

Figure 9 – Data Sovereignty Services Big Picture

The Data Agreement Service enables data transactions in a secure, trusted, and auditable way. It offers interfaces for the negotiation detailing the agreed terms for planned data exchange. The service is not meant to handle the transaction of data (that is described in the negotiated data contracts).

The Data Logging Service provides evidence that data has been (a) transmitted, (b) received and (c) that rules and obligations (Usage Policies) were successfully enforced or were violated. This supports the clearing of operational issues but also identifies fraudulent transactions.

The Provider can track if, how, and what data was provided, with the Consumer being notified about this. The Consumer can track if data was received or not, and, additionally, track and provide evidence on the enforcement or violation of Usage Policies.

4.3.3 Integration & Differences Between GAIA-X and IDS⁷

The combined architecture of GAIA-X and IDS supports and enables data spaces and builds advanced smart services in industry verticals. GAIA-X focuses on sovereign cloud services and cloud infrastructure, while IDS focuses on data and data sovereignty. The interaction of GAIA-X and IDS has three main tasks: self-sovereign data storage, trustworthy data usage and interoperable data exchange.

Figure 10 shows the mapping of the IDS components into the GAIA-X Architecture.

⁷ Source: IDS Position Paper "IDS and GAIA-X" Version 1.0 January 2021

Figure 10 – Mapping of IDS Components into the GAIA-X Architecture

The Data provider and Data Consumer are mapped into the data ecosystem whereas the Service, App and App Store Providers are mapped into the infrastructure ecosystem.

The IDS connectors can be integrated in the GAIA-X Nodes, as they work as secure gateways. Other key elements of the IDS architecture can be mapped into the GAIA-X federation services. For instance, the DAPS and Identity Provider can cover the Identity & Trust federation services. The Federated Catalogue can leverage on the IDS Broker Service Provider, the Vocabulary Provider and the IDS Information Model. The sovereign data exchange service can benefit from the IDS Clearing House and the IDS Usage Control concept. And the IDS Certification mechanisms could support the GAIA-X compliance services.

5 Data Space reference Architecture

5.1 Building blocks for Smart Energy

5.1.1 DAIRO/BDVA SRIA v.4.0

The emergent Data Economy relies on the availability of data as the basis for further innovation and exponential development of technologies. Data is the new currency underpinning the new data economy and catalysing the European economy for a faster and more effective development.

The European contractual Public Private Partnership on Big Data Value (BDV PPP) was signed in October 2014, marking the commitment of the European Commission, industry, and academia to build a data-driven economy across Europe, creating a competitive advantage for European industry, stimulating economic growth and job opportunities. Its goal is to enable the creation of a European Big Data Value economy, supporting, boosting, and mobilising stakeholders throughout society, industry, academia, and research, and delivering services and technologies, while providing highly skilled data engineers, scientists and practitioners along the entire Big Data Value chain.

The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is the private counterpart to the EU Commission in implementing the BDV PPP programme. BDVA is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation, whose members from all over Europe represent large, small, and medium-sized industries, research, and user organizations.

The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and societal benefit and achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence.

A successful implementation and adoption of a pan-European data sharing space mark a milestone in the evolution of the new data economy. Macro-level space can incorporate existing vertical, cross-sectoral, personal, and industrial data spaces, offering services and opportunities for experimentation to all involved stakeholders.

Emerging data ecosystems enable large-scale data to be securely connected, valorised, and shared through the following three complementary technologies:

1. **Data Spaces:** any ecosystem including data storage, data models, datasets, ontologies, lifecycle management platforms, protocols, data sharing contracts and specialised management services together with soft competencies around it (for example, governance, social interactions, business processes), aiming to optimize data storage and exchange mechanisms, while preserving, generating and sharing new knowledge.
2. **Data Platforms:** next generation data acquisition and processing platforms.
3. **Data Marketplaces:** enabler of the Data Economy that in analogy with well-known product-service e-commerce portals offer a one-stop-shop where data providers (sellers) and data consumers (buyers) can meet, match, and trade their respective data assets and requirements, as well as data algorithms and processing approaches. Data Marketplaces addresses the disconnected and non-interoperable nature of multiple existing data spaces, allowing to maximize data value extraction. Data Marketplaces operate on top of Data Spaces and utilize Data Sharing and Data Exchange apps provided by Data Platforms to allow the interoperability and trading of data between different subjects, often but not
4. **Exclusively as B2B.** Data are commercialized by using Open Data, Monetised Data and, Trusted Data sharing mechanisms.¹²

The realisation of a successful European-governed data sharing space able to generate economic value by broadening data access for AI, relies on a clear plan of iterative implementation strategies

and on a coordinated effort of all relevant stakeholders. The key concept of trust has a central role in successful data sharing activities: from the validity of the data itself and the algorithms operating on it to the entities governing the data space, to the enabling technologies, as well as amongst the wide variety of users.

The BDVA identifies two additional opportunities that can materialise as a result of timely interventions to converge data sharing initiatives in Europe and realise its vision:

1. Achieve wider access to data to realise the full potential of emerging AI technology by designing and implementing of a common, trustworthy, decentralised data space able to enable secure and democratic data sharing, while boosting the European data economy.
2. Achieve a European-governed data space, giving Europe a prominent role in steering international efforts to develop data and AI solutions reflecting and respecting European ethical values including democracy, privacy protection, and equality. This vision for a European-governed data sharing space should be built around and in collaboration with the same wide variety of stakeholders that can exploit its benefits as users.

The BDVA position assert that data spaces, platforms, and marketplaces are key enablers to unlock the potential of Big Data. This position is in line with the European Commission's plan to promote the development and use of "made in Europe" AI technology, supporting the call for a joint action of Member States to establish "common European data space to make data sharing across borders seamless" and thus enable "large, secure and robust datasets" for AI technology to be developed.

Several challenges must be addressed to realize this vision:

- › new business models for the industry for data-driven AI-based solutions.
- › trustworthiness in AI and its results.
- › implementation of an AI and Big Data ecosystem, overcoming the lack of data interoperability.
- › integration and development of several technologies, such as advanced data analytics, distributed AI, and hardware optimized for AI.

Figure 11: BDVA Reference Model

In 2020, BDVA was strengthened by the members, with a new mandate, expanding its scope and activities. In 2021, BDVA assumed a new name to testify the ambition of the Association to collaborate closely with other communities at the intersection of the key disciplines of Data, AI and Robotics; thus, BDVA became DAIRO.

5.1.2 FIWARE RA

The following sections elaborate on the different components FIWARE brings materializing the different technical building blocks required for creation of data spaces.

5.1.2.1 Data Interoperability Building Blocks

Data providers joining data spaces must be able to publish data resources at well-defined endpoints knowing that data consumers, a priori unknown to them, will know how to retrieve and consume data through those endpoints. Data consumers, on the other hand, must know how data available through endpoints they discover can be consumed. This is a key principle which was observed in the design of the world wide web: content providers publish web pages on web servers (endpoints) knowing that web browsers will be able to connect to them and retrieve web pages whose content they can render and display to end users. It means that all participants in data spaces should “speak the same language”, which translates into adopting domain-agnostic common APIs and security schemas for data exchange (the way of constructing sentences) together with data models represented in data formats compatible with those APIs (the vocabulary used in constructed sentences).

The NGSI API is domain-agnostic. Many different systems use NGSI not only for smart energy but also for smart cities, smart manufacturing, smart water, smart agriculture, smart ports, or smart health, to mention a few. This facilitates data sharing because each system participating in a data space will be publishing data that simply enriches a Digital Twin data representation of the world that the rest of systems connecting to the data space will know how to access. Systems

participating into the data space don't know a priori what other systems may consume the data they publish (although they will be able to set up concrete terms and conditions for accessing/using data as we will explain in the next section).

Figure 12 illustrates how different systems participating in data spaces “powered by FIWARE” will exchange data. Context Broker servers are the endpoints through which systems connected to the data space publish digital twin data, very much like web servers publish HTML content on the world wide web. Those systems can in turn connect to Context Broker servers to obtain information they need. Note that data spaces powered by FIWARE enable near real-time (right-time) exchange of digital twin data which is fundamental in the design of innovative value chains demanding a very dynamic exchange of data among participants. NGSI-LD brings quite simple and therefore easy to use operations for creating, updating, and consuming context / digital twin data but also more powerful operations like sophisticated queries, including geo-queries, or the subscription to get notified on changes of digital twin entities. On the other hand, data spaces “powered by FIWARE” can also support the exchange of large files using standard file transfer protocols, since this kind of file transfer may be required for certain scenarios like training of AI algorithms.

Figure 12 – Data Exchange in a data space “powered by FIWARE”

Note that systems participating in data spaces “powered by FIWARE” do not need to be themselves “powered by FIWARE”. Systems which have not been architected using FIWARE can still use the NGSI API to share data they produce and consume data they need in the form of data associated with attributes of digital twin entities which represent that part of the world they deal with. This can be done directly by the systems or through NGSI system adapters which implement a conversion between NGSI and the API that the system natively supports for managing data.

From a theoretical perspective, systems connected to a data space should be able to share data using the API they prefer. The specification (information model) of each API could be published as some kind of manifesto that certain components, integrated as part of the platform that systems should use to connect to the data space, can dynamically process to perform an automated adaptation from/to the APIs. However, such an approach faces important challenges. In the first place, such an approach has only been demonstrated in remarkably simple scenarios and involving quite simple APIs. Thus, the ability to exploit the sophisticated features of NGSI-LD to support for accessing digital twin data will be rather limited. On the other hand, creating a “common lingua” has proven to work for creating the kind of ecosystems we pursue: we shall ask ourselves whether the world wide web would have been as speedily adopted if HTTP and HTML had not been adopted as “common lingua” for web servers and browsers and each web server had the ability to choose a different protocol (as opposed to HTTP) or a different document format (as opposed to HTML). NGSI-LD has the advantages of being an open standard (defined by ETSI), has a strong

open-source community behind (FIWARE) and, quite relevant within Europe, it will pave the way for alignment with developments in the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program. Creation of system adapters that transform from specific APIs a given system may still require to use from/to NGSI-LD has proven to be not a complex task.

As mentioned before, the NGSI-LD API is domain-agnostic, therefore it is designed to work for any type of digital twin. Consequently, achieving full interoperability also requires the adoption of common data models to be represented in formats compatible with the API. Here, the Smart Data Models initiative reaches great relevance. It brings a powerful resource for developers who can rely on the way data model specifications are mapped into concrete JSON and JSON-LD structures under the initiative, compatible with NGSIv2 and NGSI-LD respectively.

Figure 13 illustrates how resources are organized within the Smart Data Models initiative on GitHub. Data models are grouped into “subjects” (weather, parking, aquaculture, etc) which in turn are referred to from repositories associated with the multiple application domains being considered (Smart Energy, Smart Cities, Smart Agriculture, Smart Manufacturing, Smart Water, etc). Note that there are subjects which are very specific to a given application domain (e.g., “street lighting” with regards to smart cities and communities) while others may be relevant to multiple domains (e.g., “weather” that is relevant to almost every domain or “sewage” that is relevant to the Smart Cities and Smart Water domains). Published data models are open to contributions and royalty-free.

The Smart Data Models initiative defines an open governance model specifying the lifecycle of data models comprising incubation of brand-new data models as well as curation of data models via harmonization of different contributions. Processes and procedures for management of the different activities follow best practices from open-source communities, guided by principles of transparency and meritocracy.

Figure 13: Smart Data Models organization on GitHub

Completing the picture of building blocks for Data Interoperability, FIWARE brings components which provide the means for tracing and tracking in the process of data provision and data consumption/use. It provides the basis for several essential functions, from identification of the provenance of data to audit-proof logging of NGSI-LD transactions. For those data spaces with strong requirements on transparency and certification, FIWARE brings components (i.e., Canis Major) that ease recording of transaction logs into different Distributed Ledgers / Blockchains.

5.1.2.2 Data Sovereignty and Trust Building Blocks

Data spaces must provide means for guaranteeing organizations joining data spaces that they can trust the other participants and that they will be able to exercise sovereignty on their data. That requires the definition of common building blocks, based on mature security standards that will be used by all participants in the data space.

A first fundamental building block to support within data spaces has to do with Identity Management (IM). This building block allows identification, authentication, and authorization of organizations, individuals, machines, and other actors participating in a data space. While this building block can be implemented based on third party open-source technologies like KeyCloak, just to mention one popular example, FIWARE brings the Keyrock component which supports OpenIdConnect, SAML 2.0 and OAuth2 standards. Quite relevant for data spaces deployed in Europe, Keyrock also resolves integration with eIDAS, a building block provided by the European Commission that enables the mutual recognition of national electronic identification schemes (eID) across borders, allowing European citizens to use their national eIDs when accessing online services from other European countries.

A second fundamental building block will be the one which facilitates trusted data exchange among participants, providing certainty that participants involved in the data exchange are who they claim to be, and that they comply with defined rules/agreements. Trust refers to the fact that data providers and data consumers can rely on the identity of the members of the data ecosystem and beyond that, between different security domains. Here, IDS Connector technology, as described in the IDS Reference Architecture Model (RAM) emerges as a solid basis and the FIWARE Community has incubated an open-source implementation of this technology that has already been tested on how it can integrate with the rest of core FIWARE components.

Figure 14 illustrates how an AI service provider application and an AI service consumer application, each hosted in different organizations and participating in a common data space “powered by FIWARE,” may interact with each other. It shows the role of components that are part of the incubated FIWARE IDS Connector implementation and their integration with other FIWARE components. The AI service provided can be an advanced traffic prediction service while the AI service consumer application might be a traffic management system running in each city. The AI service consumer wishes to incorporate near real-time traffic predictions based on current traffic levels measured through IoT sensors deployed in the streets. The Context Broker component running on the consumer application sends notifications based on updates on attribute “current traffic” of a given street. These updates are notified to the AI service where the value is processed in real-time applying AI algorithms (e.g. using Apache Spark). The predicted traffic in about 30 minutes is calculated (generating, for example, values “low,” “medium” or “high”) and the value of attribute “traffic in 30 minutes” of the given street is updated if changes occur.

Figure 14: Integration of FIWARE IAM and IDS Connector functionalities

In FIWARE, the implementation of IDS Connectors comes closely linked to the deployment of Kubernetes clusters. In this respect, the implementation of the concept of IDS connectors would not be limited to the implementation of the procedures used to exchange data among IDS connectors but also the monitoring and control of what is deployed in the associated clusters (e.g., guaranteeing that only certified components/applications are deployed) as well as the control of the flow of data within the cluster, ensuring enforcement of data access/usage control policies. For this last purpose, the usage of products supporting service mesh concepts like Istio are essential. In Figure 14, such components are identified as “traffic routers”.

In the IDS RAM, identity and access/usage control is currently performed at organization level. The Certification Authority (CA) and Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) oversee verifying that organizations exchanging data are known and trustworthy. The IDS Connectors ensure that data exchanges are authorized at organization level. In Figure 14, for example, the FIWARE IDS Connector running at the AI service consumer side ensures that when an IoT agent updates context / digital twin attributes on the local Context Broker (1) forwarding of updates (2) are sent out only to authorized organizations like the AI service provider in this example. The FIWARE IDS Connector running at the service provider side will in turn verify that the organization from which updates are received is a trusted party and is authorized to make such updates to be then forwarded through the FIWARE Cosmos component to Spark where AI algorithms for traffic prediction purposes run. Similarly, when updates on the Context Broker deployed at the consumer side are invoked from the AI algorithms (3), the FIWARE IDS connector at the AI service provider side verifies that only requests authorized to be transmitted will be sent out. The FIWARE IDS connector at the AI consumer side verifies that the update request received comes from a trusted and authorized organization. All these verifications take place relying on the global CA+DAPS services of the data space.

On top of this authentication and data access/usage control procedures, performed at organization level via IDS Connectors, FIWARE security components enable an additional and finer grained authentication and access control at the end user level. Therefore, coming back to Figure 14, notifications received at the AI service provider side, same as update requests handled at the AI service consumer application side carry additional security tokens (namely, Json Web Tokens - JWT) linked to users on behalf of which those notifications/requests have been issued. The API proxy components, both at the consumer and on the provider side, validate those tokens and obtain the info associated with the corresponding users relying on standard Identity Provider services supported by the FIWARE Keyrock component. For managing access control, a standard XACML process is implemented. The API proxy plays the role of the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) and the FIWARE AuthZForce component, also alternatively Keyrock, implements the Policy Decision Point (PDP) functionality. That means that the proxy forwards user info of the particular user

together with information about the concrete notification/request to the PDP which then checks whether users with those credentials are entitled to perform the given operation. FIWARE brings alternative implementations of the API proxy, namely Wilma, API Umbrella and CoatRack, all of them compatible with Keyrock or any third-party product implementing OpenID Connect, OAuth2 and XACML standards. Keyrock also implements Policy Administration Point (PAP) and Policy Management Point (PMP) standard XACML functions.

5.1.2.3 Data Value Creation Building Blocks

Loose coupling of participants is a fundamental principle in data spaces. Data providers and consumers do not necessarily know about each other. Therefore, it becomes essential to incorporate building blocks enabling the management of data resources as true assets with a business value. Assets which can be published, discovered and, eventually, traded. This way boosting the creation of multi-side markets where innovative services can be created.

FIWARE Business Application Ecosystem (BAE) components enable creation of Marketplace services which participants in data spaces can rely on for publishing their offerings around data assets they own. Distinct types of data assets can be defined via plugins, but three kinds of standard data asset types are supported by default, namely static data files, right-time data resources provided via NGSI-LD at well-defined endpoints, and data processing services, which typically have associated well defined endpoints for providing input data and publish results, both in right-time, using NGSI-LD. Marketplace services are accessible through a portal or via APIs. Users, either end users through the portal or applications via APIs, of the Marketplace service can perform the following main actions:

- › define new data asset types via plug-ins
- › register offerings around defined data asset types which typically means providing description of the asset, data models behind, endpoints (URLs) through which the data asset will be accessible and, particularly important, terms and conditions defined around the data asset, including SLAs, legal clauses, access control policies users of the asset must comply with and associated pricing schema, which may be based on:
 - Free access (open data): user pay no money
 - One-time payments: users pay only once.
 - Recurring payments: users pay periodically (monthly, yearly, etc) for getting access to some data. In addition, users will be able to cancel the subscription, but they won't be able to access data anymore.
 - Usage payment: users pay per use. Their payments are based on the amount of information consumed.
- › ability to navigate and search/discover existing offerings based on selected criteria.

Following is the list of backend components and APIs associated to the FIWARE BAE Marketplace:

- › Backend implementing standard TM Forum APIs supporting configuration of the marketplace:
 - Catalogue Management API
 - Product Ordering Management API
 - Product Inventory Management API
 - Party Management API
 - Customer Management API
 - Billing Management API
 - Usage Management API
- › Rating, Charging, and Billing backend
- › Revenue Settlement and Sharing System.
- › Authentication, API Orchestrator, and Web portal

Figure 15 shows the FIWARE Data Marketplace portal deployed.

Figure 15: FIWARE Data Marketplace portal

FIWARE also comprise components for publication of data resources linked to data assets around which offerings are managed through the FIWARE Data Marketplace. For this purpose, we have the Idrá publication platform and an extended version of the CKAN open data platform, which is an open data publication platform widely adopted in the market. These extensions support enhanced data management capabilities and integration with FIWARE technologies including NGSI. In particular, data publication and discovery features provided by CKAN have been enhanced with the following features:

- › Right-time (near real time) time data publication - thanks to this extension, CKAN is not limited to list data resources linked to static files as part of its catalogue but also data resources linked to NGSI-LD requests served by Context Broker components deployed in a data space. This brings the ability to discover data resources relying on DCAT capabilities publication platforms support,
- › Identity Management, Authentication and Access Control functions based on Keyrock components - therefore supporting OpenId Connect, OAuth2 and XACML standards adopted at overall data space level.
- › Publication of priced data resources - thanks to this extension, it is possible to mark data resources listed as part of the catalogue as linked to offerings visible in the Data Marketplace. Users can therefore click on those data resources and navigate to the Marketplace to proceed with the acquisition of access rights

Enhanced Data Visualization - thanks to this extension WireCloud (Configurable Dash-boards component) to create adaptive and incremental data visualization. This way, farmers (sellers) can decide the way they want their data to be shown.

5.1.2.4 Elements for a Reference Architecture with FIWARE components

The reference architecture of FIWARE platform for energy include quite different components that allow the integration with data spaces. The different elements can operate stand-alone or integrated into an ecosystem of solutions. The use of NGSI standard for accessing the information simplifies the data interchange. Eventually, any of the boxes describing a system can be replaced by other solutions, or eventually for the legacy systems already present in the pilots.

Figure 16: FIWARE Reference Architecture

The context broker is the core of the architecture. It allows the connection in right time with more than 800 updates a second which is useful for most of use cases in energy sector. It can integrate the data coming from different elements of the architecture and to define subscriptions to any event worth to be noticed. In example when a sensor measurement exceeds a specific value. Once the event happens an alert is sent to the connected system.

Figure 17: FIWARE Context Broker

The context broker allows to retrieve the information from heterogenous systems connected and defined as a data source. This is a powerful mechanism, the federation, which allows the extension in the data sources but also in the processing capacity of the system. The information stored there comply with the NGSi standard. This standard stores the data into entities composed of properties and relationships, as drafted in the example in the following image.

Figure 18: Example of FIWARE Entities complying with the NGSI standard

These entities define the elements to be controlled and managed. A series of attributes provide details about these elements. This information can be updated on a real-time basis (e.g., consumption), or rarely (e.g., maximum power produced).

To provide interoperability, the entities defined in some systems should be compatible with the same entity in other systems. The Smart Data Models Initiative has documented the different entities according to existing standards and actual experiences. Currently more than 400 data models are defined including the Common Information Model for Energy⁸, battery⁹, other data models for elements Energy¹⁰, including consumption¹¹, the use of devices for measuring the different magnitudes, but also some out-of-domain data models related like weather¹² or environmental impact¹³.

5.1.3 Integration of FIWARE & IDS/GAIA-X

A fundamental building block will be the one which facilitates trusted data exchange among participants, providing certainty that participants involved in the data exchange are who they claim to be, and that they comply with defined rules/agreements. Trust refers to the fact that data providers and data consumers can rely on the identity of the members of the data ecosystem and beyond that, between different security domains. Here, IDS Connector technology, as described in the IDS Reference Architecture Model (RAM)¹⁴ emerges as a solid basis. FIWARE Community has

⁸ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.EnergyCIM>

⁹ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Battery>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Energy>

¹¹ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Device/tree/master/SmartMeteringObservation>

¹² <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Weather>

¹³ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Environment>

¹⁴ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/download/16630/>

incubated an open-source implementation of this technology that has already been tested how it can integrate with the rest of core FIWARE components.

GAIA-X aims at creating a federated form of data infrastructure in Europe which strengthens the ability to both access and share data securely and confidently. Since its creation, the initiative has raised a lot of awareness because of the opportunity it brings to join forces and, leveraging existing assets, accelerate delivery of solutions to the market.

IDSA is providing several architecture elements which are necessary to create data spaces with trust and data sovereignty being some of the most important ones. These are necessary but not sufficient to create real living data spaces which are accepted and adapted on the market. Standard APIs, standard data models as well as marketplace functionalities are also necessary. The complementarities of both initiatives regarding technology building blocks are illustrated in Figure 19. As the FIWARE Context Broker technology was adopted in 2019 as one of the Building Blocks of the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program and has proven to integrate smoothly with other relevant CEF Building Blocks for the creation of Data Spaces (e.g., eIDAS, EBSI), this allows the alignment between these initiatives. As a result, the close partnership between FIWARE and IDSA is guaranteeing the aligned contribution of both ecosystems to the success of data spaces based on GAIA-X.

Figure 19: IDSA and FIWARE positioning to create Data Spaces.

5.2 High level functional model for Vocabularies

5.2.1 AIOTI HLA

In the following, the High Level IoT architecture, release 5.0 considerations of the use of ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010 by AIOTI is presented and analysed for the purposes of the I-ENERGY. In summary, it:

- > presents a Domain Model and discusses the “thing” in IoT
- > presents a Functional Model (Figure 20)
- > introduces the Identifiers for IoT
- > provides deployment considerations related to relevant IoT architectural matters such as cloud and edge computing, Big Data, virtualization, security, privacy and (platform) interoperability
- > links this work with the AIOTI WG03 Semantic Interoperability work and the Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) Landscape work

- › provides mapping examples to some existing SDO/Alliances' architectural work related to functional models: ITU-T, oneM2M, BDVA
- › establishes the link to other architectures and frameworks such as Big Data and IoT-enabled Data Marketplaces
- › The layers view in the 3D model, see Figure 21, characterises IoT Systems from a functional and operational perspective. It includes aspects from physical devices, networking, cloud infrastructures, data, services and applications but also collaboration and administration. The main aim of this view is to facilitate the identification of the necessary functional blocks for interoperability at the different layers in IoT systems.

Figure 20: AIOTI High-level Functional Model

AIOTI HLA is typically deployed using cloud infrastructures. Cloud-native principles can be applied to ensure scaling and resilience for IoT. In certain use cases, deploying edge cloud infrastructures, will be beneficial to allow data processing locally. AIOTI designed its HLA to allow for distributed intelligence, it is therefore compatible with Cloud and Edge computing. It has the following objectives:

- › Big Data: collecting, storing and sharing data is an integral part of IoT, therefore also for AIOTI HLA. Big Data can be seen as the set of disciplines, such as storing, analysing, querying and visualization of large data sets. Those disciplines are equally applicable to IoT data sets.
- › Virtualization: ensuring flexibility and scale is one of the major challenges for deploying IoT. Virtualization would help scaling IoT for a large number of use cases.
- › The 3D IoT Layered Architecture (aka the 3D model), is an approach to define, identify and correlate multiple IoT system features, architectural characteristics and properties in Large Scale pilot (LSP) IoT systems.
- › The principle of this Reference Architecture is to use a number of 2D views that are a projection of the 3D view on a specific plane. The Figure 20 depicts the three main views in the 3D Model (Layers, Cross-cutting functions, and Properties).

Figure 21: AIOTI 3D HLA

- The Figure 22 depicts the layers components, cross-cutting functions example and properties mapping.

Figure 22: Layers view of 3D

5.3 Building blocks for Ontologies

The data space concept or principle and GAIA-X reference architecture model for data exchange and interoperability is very important in Modelling AI assets. This data space and its data and infrastructure reference architecture model (RAM) proposals has ontology as one of its very important ecosystem for knowledge gathering, representation, management and inference in

Artificial intelligence application. As a relation-based data model, ontology has its foundation in resource description framework (RDF) from which the world wide web consortium (W3C) came about the web ontology language (OWL). The data space concept and GAIA-X infrastructure will represent relational or graph-based knowledge through the consideration of ontology as part of the data and infrastructure ecosystem.

The importance of ontology is COSMAG's main goal of sector coupling involving open API and data exchange standard, which extends SGAM. Also, Ontology importance is mentioned in the European Union BRIDGE reference architecture under the information layer within the middle cross-domain vertical of the interoperability layer, as seen in Section 4.3. And to cap it all, one of the motivations of the GAIA-X project is the challenges faced by lack of ontology in sector specific data spaces as mentioned in Section 4.4.2.1.

Since data model involving ontology reveals more information or context about the data, there is a need for data provenance, data sovereignty and data security in how data is stored, exchanged, and used across AI applications. This ontological data transaction has to be done with the EU's GDPR and IPR guidelines, which will give the citizens the rest of mind to give access to their data. IDS and GAIA-x reference has demonstrated a federated platform of trust for ontological data and also as a safe haven for all form of data usage, data exchange and data storage transactions.

This section will introduce the smart application reference architecture (**SAREF**), **BRICKS** and the **BIM** as the building blocks and important domain, and upper or general ontology types that forms the relational data ecosystem for the data space and the GAIA-X reference architecture model. **SARGON** and **DTDL** (Digital Twin Description Language) are also other very important ontologies that combines some concept in the grid domain and the building domain and were already discussed in section 4 of D3.1.

5.3.1 Smart Reference Architecture (SAREF) Ontology

The Smart application reference ontology standard, which was originally known as smart appliance reference architecture, is intended to enable interoperability between different provider solutions and those actively involved in the Internet of Things technology (IoT). It also aims to contribute to the global digital economy regarding development of smart applications. SAREF is a consensus model among the stakeholders that allows the matching of existing assets in the smart application domain. The SAREF reference ontology basically provides the building block that enables the separation and recombination of the different part of the ontology depending on the particular needs of the use case.

The original idea of SAREF started as a study of the available semantic asset for the interoperability of smart appliances by mapping it into a common ontology as a machine-to-machine application layer semantic. The study shows that energy conservation in smart appliances is achievable if those appliances is managed on a system level. Nevertheless, the appliances need standardized interfaces to achieve interoperability. On an individual level, standards exists but not on a common platform which made the devices to be somewhat fragmented. So, a reference ontology was agreed upon to be designed for the appliances to ensure energy efficiency [1]. SAREF also used the SAREF Communication framework as defined in the ETSI TS 103267 of the SmartM2M; Smart Appliance Communication Framework.

However, the main principle of SAREF is in its shared model of consensus, which gives rise to matching of existing semantic assets. That is, maintaining the semantic narratives of disparate systems or devices. This reduces the transaction of terminology of one asset to another since SAREF requires one set of mapping to each asset instead of a dedicated set of mapping for each pair of asset. SAREF's approach is seen in their findings that different semantic asset share some recurring core concept despite using different terminologies and different data model to portray this concepts. Therefore, **semantic interoperability** in smart application is SAREF main core

concept. Semantic interoperability in smart-home using a distributed platform based on established web standard was proposed in [2].

The following fundamental principle gives rise to the creation of SAREF:

- > Reuse and Alignment of the concept and relationship that are defined in the existing asset
- > Modularity to allow the tearing and build-up of the different part of the ontology depending on the specific needs
- > Extensibility to allow the continuous growth of the ontology
- > Maintainability to enable the process of identifying and corecting the defect, accommodate new requirements and cope with changes in SAREF.

Figure 5.3.1-1 shows an overview of the SAREF ontology with the twelve (12) classes and their relationships with each other.

Figure 5.3.1-1 – The SAREF Ontology overview [3]

SAREF Core Classes

SAREF has about 12 core class or concepts that forms the upper class or the super class of the saref ontology reference architecture. These classes have subclasses with attributes and various relationships among these classes and subclasses. SAREF core classes are [3]:

- > **Device:** A tangible object designed to accomplish a particular task in household, common public building or office.
- > **Command:** A directive that a device shall support to perform a certain function.
- > **Function:** The function necessary to accomplish a task for which a device is designed.
- > **Service:** A representation of a function to a network that makes that function discoverable, registrable, and remotely controllable by other devices in the network.
- > **Measurement:** This is the measured value made over a property
- > **Unit of measurement:** The unit of measurement is a standard of measurement of a quantity, such as **saref:Property**
- > **Commodity:** A marketable item for which there is a demand, but which is supplied without qualitative differentiation across a market.
- > **Task:** This is the goal for which a device is designed (from a user view).
- > **State:** The state in which a device can be found; eg On state or OFF state
- > **Property:** Anything that is sensed, measured or controlled in households common public building or office.

- › **Profile:** A specification associated to a device to collect information about a certain property or commodity (e.g. Energy or Water) for optimizing its usage in the home/building in which the device is located.
- › **Feature of interest:** This represents any real world entity from which a property is measured

SAREF Serialization Format

SAREF has five main serialization formats for: exchanging data across a network, for storing data as a file in a computer, for writing data in a database or for in-memory processing of data.. These serialization formats include:

- › JSON-LD: JavaScript Object Notation Linked Data.
- › N3: Which means Notation 3 is a non-XML serialization of RDF developed by Tim Bernes-Lee from the semantic web community. N3 is a superset of Turtle.
- › N-Tripples: This is a line-based/text based RDF serialization format for storing and transmitting data. It is a subset of Turtle.
- › RDF/XML: This is the first serialization format based on Extensible mark-up language
- › Turtle: Which means Terse RDF Triple Language is a sybtax and file format for expressing data in the RDF data model. Turtle syntax is similar to that of SPARQL.

SAREF Extension

SAREF contains recurring concepts that are used in several domains. Since smart appliances are not confined, it is possible that specific concept for a certain domain are not part of SAREF. To handle these new concepts and provide different domain with a good ontology that reflects the particular need of that domain, extension to SAREF need to be created. Figure 23shows SAREF as the upper model to be used as a basis for creating extensions in different domain.

Figure 23: SAREF and its extension [1]

More of the SAREF ontology extensions which are applicable to some use cases in projects and subgroups as listed in the table below[4]. There can be more than one extension in each domain depending on the need and the domain complexity. Table 3 below shows more of the extension of SAREF and the date the extension was implemented.

Subgroup and Projects	Abbreviation	Date of extension
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SAREF for Smart lifts	Saref4lift	August 2021
SAREF for Building Domain	SAREF4BLDG	August 2021
SAREF for Environment Domain	SAREF4ENVI	August 2021
SAREF for Smart Cities Domain	SAREF4CITY	August 2021
SAREF for Industry and Manufacturing Domain	SAREF4INMA	August 2021
SAREF for Smart Agriculture and Food Chain Domain	SAREF4AGRI	August 2021
SAREF for eHealth/Ageing-well	SAREF4EHAW	August 2021
SAREF for Automotive	SAREF4AUTO	August 2021
SAREF for Wearables	SAREF4WEAR	August 2021
SAREF for Water	SAREF4WATR	August 2021
saref extension for systems connections between systems	saref4syst	August 2021
SAREF Core ontology		August 2021
	saref-core	
saref-pipeline	saref-pipeline	July August
saref-portal	saref-portal	July August
SAREF for Energy ontology	saref4ener	July August
saref-server	saref-server	July August

Table 3: SAREF subgroup and project with date of extension

5.3.2 BRICK Ontology

BRICK is an ontology that represents the entities, attributes and relationship of a building as a system and all the components of the building. It is an open source initiative to enable the semantic description of physical, logical and virtual assets in buildings and their relationship for standardization among stakeholders. The Quantity, Unit, Dimension and data Type (QUDT) ontology gave rise to BRICK. The lack of expressivity, amongst other limitations, in Haysatck also gave rise to BRICK ontology. One of the main advantages of BRICKS is that it has an extensible dictionary of terms and concept in the building ecosystems with a set of relationships for linking and composing these terms together and a very flexible data model that allows the bringing together of BRICK with current tools and databases. Figure 5.3.2 shows the design principle that Brick conforms to [5].

Figure 5.3.2-1: BRICK Design Principle

Brick ontology has the following as essential core concepts:

- > Entity
 - > Tag
 - > Class
 - > Relationship
 - > Graph
- A. **Entity** is an abstraction of any physical, logical or virtual item which is known as “thing” in a building. Physical entity is the real tangible thing or asset we can see and feel. Examples are mechanical equipment’s like Air Handling Unit (AHU), Variable Air Volume (VAV) Box, Luminaires and Lighting Systems (LLS), electrical meters, thermostats, eV chargers, and spatial elements like rooms and floors.
Virtual entities are digital or intangible replicas of concepts, which are usually within a software system. Examples of virtual entities are the value of a temperature sensor, the heat of the sun, the speed of a fan or the humidity of a space or zone.
Logical entities are those concepts that are defined by a set of rules. HVAC zones and lighting zones are examples of logical entities.
 - B. **Tag** is a minute or atomic fact of a concept. Tag is a borrowed concept from the Haystack Tag Ontology (HTO) to keep the flexibility and ease of use for annotation. BRICK does not totally rely on tag to determine the type of a concept.
 - C. **Class** is a way of categorizing concepts or terms with the intention of grouping them into meaningful entities. Classes are arranged into a taxonomy or hierarchy until the last entity of concept, which is, known as an instance or individual.
 - D. **Relationship** describes the type of link between two connected entities. Examples of relationship are:
 - **Instantiation:** where one concept type is given by another concept in the form of inheritance.
 - **Sequence:** Where within a process, one concept occurs before the next one in sequence.
 - **Encapsulation:** Where one concept is inside another concept.

- E. **Graph** is a tree-like data structure, which represents a set of concepts (vertices or nodes) and relationships (edges or links) in an RDF model. BRICKS is represented as a labelled graph data type. Figure 5.3.2-2 shows graph as an RDF concept.

Table 4: Graph as an RDF concept

Philosophy of BRICK Relationship

Relationship is the fundamental principle behind ontology and the BRICK model. It expresses how the concept which is made up of entities, classes, tags and other “things” interact and link with each other. It defines the nature of the association between two concepts. It also defines the meaning of the **predicate** in the RDF triple. The BRICK relationship has a *subject* (the concept or “thing” that owns the relationship or the concept or “thing” that the relationship is about) and an *object* (the concept or “thing” that is the value of the relationship). The BRICK building relationship perspectives is described by [6]:

- > Composition
- > Topology
- > Telemetry

The usage of BRICK relationship is a function of when the subject of the triple model is a **location**, a **point** or an **equipment**.

The BRICK model

The BRICK model is a digital replica of a building that conforms to the BRICK schema. The BRICK model is a typical implementation of ontology using the above core concepts. Entities in a BRICK model are classified with respect to the BRICK hierarch or taxonomy and the relationship concerned as defined by the BRICK model. Figure 5.3.2-3 shows the BRICK model with all the core concept represented.

Table 5: The BRICK Model [5]

5.3.3 Building Information Model (BIM) Ontology

Architectural engineering and construction (AEC) domain ontology is paramount in the data space and GAIA-X's data and infrastructural ecosystem RAM. Data exchange and data interoperability using Building information modelling is very crucial in avoiding energy crisis, achieving energy efficiency and reduction in CO2 level in our environment. HVAC systems ontology data in the energy domain and BIM ontology data needs to interoperate to achieve the goals of using less scarce material and enhancing the reduction of global warming while maintaining the beauty of historic and heritage buildings.

The Industry Foundation Class (IFC) enhances interoperability and data exchange in the AEC industry. IFC data model or standard enables BIM's geometrical or spatial ontological data model and have successfully been translated to OWL in the ifcOWL standard. BIM is very essential in geometric modeling, data modeling and process modeling in the AEC industry and forms the foundation of the technologies in defining ontology for the construction domain. The IFC data format can comprehensively describe the entire building and give a detail information of the BIM. BIM model its data using IFC's Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD), Universal Modeling language (UML) and Extensible Mark-up Language (XML).

The vocabularies and semantics of concepts as well as their relationships in the AEC domain is crucial in the data space and GAIA-X reference architecture for exchange and interoperability of data among stakeholders. BIM ontology is also very essential in building an artificial intelligent-based energy on demand application. This will enable knowledge representation and reasoning, for which these ecosystems of data and infrastructure will function as a formidable data storage and data usage during its exchange among the data producers and data consumers. These vocabularies and semantic in the BIM concepts and relationships data geometry will help in the Computer Aided Design (CAD) information sharing among stakeholders in building AI applications and achieving the end goal of the I-ENERGY project.

Figure 24 is the schematic overview of the part 2 of ISO 12006. It conceptualizes the basis of numerous classification system and the buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD). It shows a typical ontology in a construction scenario which is typical of BIM i.e. how the construction process, construction result and construction resources gives rise to different BIM entities with its attributes and relationships. This process, result and resources has a one-or-many relationship with its property/characteristic parent class.

Figure 24: the schematic overview of the part 2 of ISO 12006 bSDD [7]

Despite IFC being a neutral open data format for the AEC industry, lack of meaning to many BIM data has greatly hindered its use as application deployment. Ontology technology can be used to enable the exchange of information to facilitate intelligence for information integration and knowledge representation and reasoning. The work of [8] reviews the current research on ontology development in the area of BIM and proposes an intelligent application framework for facilitating data exchange and interoperability that could be adopted in the data space reference architecture model. Figure 25 shows the proposed BIM and ontology based intelligent application framework.

Figure 25 - BIM and ontology-based intelligent application framework [8]

Comparison of SAREF, BRICK and BIM Ontology

The analysis of ontologies that can fit into the data space and GAIA-X reference architecture model and the possible consideration of SAREF, BRICK or BIM is highly important. Its fundamental pros and cons for the I-ENERGY project will need to be looked into. There will be a need to compare these three ontologies and then decide which will be applicable to the use cases for the I-ENERGY project as well as also be in synergy with the AI4EU objectives. Table 6: Comparison of SAREF, BRICK and

BIM based on Modelling Support below compare these three ontologies with respect to the modelling support they all have in common.

Modelling Support	SAREF	BRICK	BIM
HVAC Systems	No	Yes	Yes
Lighting Systems	No	Yes	Yes
Electrical systems	No	Yes	Yes
Spatial Information	No	Yes	Yes
Sensors Systems	Yes	Yes	Generic
Control relationship	Yes	Yes	Generic
Operational relationship	No	Yes	Generic
Formal definitions	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 6: Comparison of SAREF, BRICK and BIM based on Modelling Support

5.3.4 FIBO

FIBO, which is an acronym for Financial Industrial Business Ontology, is an ontology, which will most likely could cover the financial, EPC contract and investment risk terminology domain in the I-ENERGY project. Pilots such as VEOLIA, that are under the building perspective and deal with end users, assets and external market conditions might have a lot of vocabulary and terms from the financial and business domain. This includes PARITY, ZEZ and FAEN pilots.

5.3.5 KM4CITY

KM4CITY stands for Knowledge Model for the smart city. It has vocabularies or terminologies for the smart city including terms for electric vehicles (eVs), charging stations and Battery management System (BMS). SONCE and REA pilot partners have data from eVs and hence the need to model the data will come from these pilots with a proper knowledge representation. HERON/PARITY pilots will also have data from eVs that might need to be modelled with their properties and relationships.

5.4 Mapping of I-ENERGY Use Cases to AI4EU

The I-ENERGY project consists of 9 pilots, with a total of 15 use cases and 2 test-bed facilities. The test-bed facilities are located in Germany and Greece, while the pilots are distributed over 7 European countries.

The demonstrations that will be carried out within the I-ENERGY project aim to test the tools and the platform implemented within the project, in line with the AI4EU European plan.

The pilots will collect and share big amount of datasets and will test different tools related to the role of artificial intelligence in the energy sector. Three kind of use cases are carried out in the project: those related to "Energy commodities networks", others related to "Distributed energy resources" and still others to "Energy Efficiency and Non-energy related Services". The table below shows the subdivision of the use cases according to this classification.

Pilot	Energy Commodities Networks	Distributed Energy Resources	Energy Efficiency and Non-Energy related Services
Pilot 1 (RDN/REN)	UC1, UC2		

Pilot 2 (VEOLIA)	UC3	UC4	UC5
Pilot 3 (ASM)	UC6	UC7	UC8
Pilot 4 (BFP)		UC9	
Pilot 5 (IRON)		UC10	
Pilot 6 (ZEZCoop)		UC11	
Pilot 7 (SONCE)			UC12
Pilot 8 (REA)			UC13
Pilot 9 (FAEN)			UC14, UC15

Table 7: Use Case classification

- LSP1 is located in Portugal and managed by the local TSO R&D NESTER, interested in improving the fault localization and countermeasures activations and the forecasting activities related to consumption/production among the EHV/HV grid. The main dataset, that the TSO will share with I-ENERGY consortium, consists of COMTRADE fault record data, composed of one .CFG and .DAT files per incident. Information related to voltage, currents and incidents characteristics are injected into the I-ENERGY infrastructure.
- LSP 2 is VEOLIA's system, that presents approximately 3,300 meters distributed throughout the Spanish territory and the annual amount of energy they measure with these devices is more than 1 million MWh. VEOLIA is sharing with the consortium the available databases with characteristic of each area (type of buildings, estimated consumption, etc) and historical weather data available of each area. The datasets will be fundamental to the multi-targets of VEOLIA, as a profit-oriented DHN designer, as an advanced ESCO and a sustainability supporter FM.
- LSP3 is managed by ASM, that operates as DSO in the city of Terni. The DN is characterized by 65,000 LV users, supplied by means of about 600 secondary substations, with a total installed capacity of about 250 MW; the average daily energy distributed is about 890 MWh. The DN management improvement is investigated through the available datasets. Smart Meters data related to heterogeneous type of customers scattered in the city, a PMU in 1 Secondary Substation and in 1 Primary Substation are the main datasets of LSP3. The I-ENERGY project will sustain ASM to analyse distribution network asset data and derive predictive maintenance schedule, to derive probabilistic forecast for generation and consumption under consideration of meteorological forecast and to analyse distribution network flexibility potential.
- LSP4 is focused on BFP RES generation plants in Puglia region (Italy) and consist of an industrial-scale medium-size Poly-crystalline Silicon PV farm with module-level smart inverters within an operational malt production plant, accounting 498 kWp of peak power, two utility-scale PV plants with nominal power around 0.9 MWp; a data hub which includes BFP operated PV-plant level SCADA electrical measurement data over 6 PVs plants. The datasets provided by BFP are related to weather information, like temperature and solar irradiation, assets specification (e.g. line / transformer parameters), asset location data, network topology, electrical data of assets, like voltages per phase, active and reactive power, loading, and the number of outages with correspondent durations. The datasets will allow to the development of innovative portfolio maintenance to reduce operational infrastructure costs.
- LSP5 HERON is the largest private energy supplier in Greece and provides electricity to multiple home or businesses that are equipped with EV charging stations. HERON supported by PARITY will collect data on the EV charging behaviour of drivers to identify average EV charging transaction duration, frequency of chargers per vehicle, time of day that most charges occur, types and capacity of chargers used. The data shared with I-ENERGY consortium are information from EV charging stations, real-time status update, charging station status (available, occupied, charging, fault, finishing), charging capacity (kW), kWh charged in current session, duration and kWh per past session, end reason for past sessions. The I-ENERGY project will enable HERON/PARITY to present data related to electricity demand in building and EV charging stations in a user friendly way,

focusing on spatial representation. Moreover, the project will be useful to efficiently manage EV charging stations and integrate variable pricing to incentivize drivers at specific intervals.

- LSP 6 is located in Croatia and operated by ZEZcoop. The pilot consists of UC 11, in which a Virtual Energy Community consisting of 100 prosumers will test peer-to-peer energy trading and auxiliary services for the grid. The objective of the pilot is to investigate the opportunities for prosumers to take stock of ancillary services in the electricity market, support policy changes due to the development of energy communities and demonstrate the impact of active participation of prosumers on the energy market. The pilot will be based on the following infrastructure: PV plants totaling 500-1000 kW, 100 prosumers, local sensors monitoring environmental data. Through smart meters distributed in the territory the Pilot will identify a recurrent profile of user behavior and through the day after forecasting of PV production Demand Response will be enabled.-
- LSP 7 is contracted to SONCE, Slovenia. The purpose of UC 12 is to increase the quality of life for users through smart living and ambient assisted living. Tools that can identify behavior profiles, event classification, and anomaly recognition will be tested. Smart meters play an essential role in the pilot. The goals are to provide customers with non-energy services for safety and comfort enhancement, with the ambition also to enrich SONCE's existing platform for P2P exchanges with the addition of non-energy services. The infrastructure consists of a 220-resident building called "Home for elderly Lenart", PV systems, thermal storage and other environmental sensors. The pilot will test predictive tools of PV production for the realization of demand response mechanisms and will test the non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) algorithm to analyze user behavior profiles.
- LSP 8 is contracted to REA and is being pursued in Latvia. It aims to facilitate investments in energy efficiency, overcoming barriers and limiting risks. As a result of UC 13, Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) and other energy investment indicators will be made more reliable and of better quality. Artificial intelligence models will be used to provide investors and financial institutions with the ability to assess very quickly and clearly the results of the energy efficiency intervention. Data from past and present energy efficiency projects will be used to perform in-depth risk analysis. Machine learning tools will be tested to predict energy consumption and calculate savings from interventions. In the pilot, a service will be tested that assesses in advance the energy savings benefits of each planned intervention, with associated financial risk.
- LSP 9 is located in Spain (Asturias region) and the Pilot leader is FAEN. The LSP is divided into two UCs, the UC14 and the UC15. UC14 wants to contribute to the realization of the next generation Energy Performance Assessment and Certification, so that they can be more accurate, reliable, user-friendly, better quality and EU-legislation compliant, while contributing to remove "reliability" barriers (which are currently hindering the high potential of EPCs to realise significant energy efficiency in the building sector). Data is being collected from historical EPC databases in Asturias region and Cadastral data. The services to be tested in this UC are the Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement, and the EPC data exploitation. UC15 wants to use artificial intelligence to predict how climate change will impact local (high resolution) renewable generation, mainly focus on solar energy at regional level, to support policy makers in the planning of the deployment of renewable sources in an effective manner. The pilot will analyze data from Copernicus, Cadastre, LiDAR, and weather providers, as well as historical data from solar radiation and temperature collected from the regional weather stations of FAEN. LSP9 The service that will be tested in this UC is the Climate change solar radiation forecasting.

As shown in the descriptive list of pilots the services to be tested fall within the objectives of AI4EU, with particular reference to I-nergy assets. Note Chapter 6 for further information about the AI4EU architecture.

Several tools belonging to different categories such as AlaaS (Artificial Intelligence as a service) and Machine Learning models are tested within the project, in addition to the development of some innovative platforms or communication channels.

As far as AlaaS tools are concerned, these are, without any claim to completeness, the optimisation of the electricity production mix, based on consumption (UC5), the optimisation of district heating network operations (UC 3), the realisation of digital twins of portions of the electricity grid (UCs 7, 8 and 10) or digital twins of buildings (UC 14), in order to have an optimal knowledge of the component and to use it in the best way, possibly even creating new tools (new generation EPC for buildings).

On the other hand, machine learning models are implemented mainly to predict trends and behaviour. Attempts are made to predict the amount of energy that can be exchanged in demand response mechanisms (UCs 7, 8, 11 and 12), as well as to predict generation and consumption on the following day (UCs 2, 3, 5, 7, 11 and 12) or how solar radiation will evolve over time due to climate change, with a local approach (UC 15). ML is also used to recognise and then predict user behaviour and consequently identify any anomalies (UCs 7, 8, 11 and 12).

And finally, machine learning models are tested in evaluating predictive maintenance activities applied to DER sources (UC 4), circuit breakers (UC 1) and transformers and power lines (UC 6).

In addition, other services necessary for the success of the project are also evaluated in the model, such as blockchain communication for energy transitions, or the implementation of marketplaces and dashboards for electricity consumption centres.

6 I-ENERGY Platform Conceptual Architecture

In the following figure the conceptual architecture of I-ENERGY is presented along with the interconnection with AI4EU platform.

Figure 26: Platform Conceptual Architecture

Specifically, the envisioned conceptual architecture consists of several groups of services, namely the Data Management Services, the Energy Analytics Services and Applications, the AI models Training Suite, along with the modules for Security and Access Control and for trusted B2B data sharing through Blockchain. All the aforementioned services will be deployed independently as microservices while the communication among them will be conducted through APIs or asynchronous messages (Publish Subscribe communication model). Moreover, it is worth mentioning that the services and resources provided by the project EGI-ACE15 will be considered to be used for training complex AI models. On the other hand, datasets and AI services, developed in the context of I-ENERGY project, will be considered to be hosted to GAIA-X16 Federated data infrastructure.

The assets that I-ENERGY provides are AI services through APIs (AlaaS), Applications and Dashboards, Datasets, code and libraries, AI models and Documentation. These assets can be utilised by different EPES users. They can be published to AI4EU catalogue, as well. Moreover, several services will be provided as docker containers along with the proper protobuf configuration to be onboarded to AI4EU Experiments platform.

By publishing assets to AI4EU catalogue and onboarding services to AI4EU Experiments platform, more **interested** stakeholders can access them through the Single Sign On (SSO) mechanism of AI4EU, which controls the identity of the users as well as their rights to the assets.

More information about each group of services is provided in the following subsections.

6.1 An I-ENERGY – AI4EU Interconnection layer which leverages on Open APIs

AI4EU, the European AI on Demand Platform, is central to the architecture of the I-ENERGY platform. A bidirectional interaction between the two platforms exists, expressing the common vision of sharing AI resources and fostering innovation among Europe's AI landscape. Towards this direction, an investigation of AI4EU resources that will potentially contribute to the development of the I-ENERGY models and services has already taken place. In addition, I-ENERGY consortium plans to make the produced assets available for the AI4EU community through the AI4EU platform offerings. This includes the AI catalogue of the AI4EU platform, where I-ENERGY assets such as AI models and services can be published, as well as the AI4EU experiments platform marketplace where I-ENERGY services adhering to the requirements of the platform can be published. On top of the sharing of the AI assets, I-ENERGY is also in close collaboration with AI4EU in terms of dissemination and community engagement activities.

In order to clarify the interconnection between I-ENERGY and AI4EU platform a dedicated deliverable, D2.4- Specifications of I-ENERGY - AI4EU Cross-fertilisation, Synergies and Alignment, is produced describing in detail the AI4EU platform offerings as well as the I-ENERGY approach to contributing to AI4EU platform along with the requirements for the alignment of the two platforms. Moreover, Deliverable 2.4 provides a detailed example covering the phases of development, onboarding to AI4EU experiments platform, creating a solution using the platform's Design Studio and deploying the solution locally. In addition to D2.4, another deliverable, D4.1 - I-ENERGY Analytics Applications (1st technology release), showcases the process of development, onboarding to AI4EU experiments platform and local deployment of an energy load forecasting service.

6.2 Data Services Layers

The I-ENERGY data service layer acts as a mediator between the I-ENERGY data providers and the data consumers who will use them in the context of the AI Trained models and Energy Analytics application layers where specific ML models, tools and services will be developed. Different energy and non-energy data, such as: real-time data generated by IoT technologies (e.g. energy consumption and energy production using smart meters, sensor-based data), historical data for model development and pattern recognition (e.g. old weather data, energy costs) and open data from heterogeneous sources such as weather data, climate, EPCs SECAPs, costs, EC datasets etc will be ingested and processed by the I-ENERGY Data Services layer.

The I-ENERGY Data Service layer has been designed to provide functionalities for the data ingestion, data harmonisation and semantic annotation, data streaming, and the data storing/querying of the different data sources.

Figure 27: Data service Layer

Data ingestion phase is ensured by an Interoperability Service module that will be in charge of facilitating the integration of data from heterogeneous sources and/or platforms such as structured and unstructured data, real-time data, data stream, IoT device data (smx, smart meters, sensors etc ..) owned by different I-ENERGY internal and external actors and served under different protocols and standards.

Data harmonisation phase is ensured by the Homegenisation module which is in charge the data pre-processing activities for data cleansing, data curation, data anonymization and data modelling leveraging on pre-existing vocabularies and ontologies that will contribute to build the I-ENERGY common data model. A Streaming module will manage the data streaming for the I-ENERGY AI Trained models and Energy Analytics application layers for the in-memory processing of the data in near real time with low latency.

Data storage phase ensure that a sub-sets of integrated and harmonised data will be stored into a specific database or into the file system based on the needs of the different services and tools of the project.

In Figure 28 the first version of the Data Services layer conceptual architecture is presented.

Figure 28: I-ENERGY Data Service layer conceptual architecture

6.2.1 Interoperability Service module

The Interoperability Service module (see Figure 29) has in charge of integrating and managing heterogeneous data from different sources and/or platforms in the energy ecosystem and beyond. These data, both historical or in real-time will be shared by the I-ENERGY Data Providers through several technologies such as IoT devices, Smart meter, SMX, Sensors, EV charging station, BEMS system, etc. Others data could be provided also via external platform that collect open data such as demographic data, economic data, cadastre etc.. that could be not necessary related to the world of energy but fundamental for the development of ML models.

The Interoperability Service module will be based on specific data connectors developed as micro-services to manage the different data provided in different formats and communication protocols (Rest APIs, SFTP, IoT protocols, Sensor Network). It will provide also interfaces to other energy and non-energy datasets/platforms of third parties and external datasets/platforms.

This module will also be able to cover data exchange mechanisms at the EDGE level, with the aim of offering both local computing power and storage capacity to services and functions that may need ultra-low latency, as well as local processing without exploiting the remote services of the core cloud. Figure 29 shows the high level *Interoperability module conceptual architecture*.

Figure 29: Interoperability module conceptual architecture

module

The purpose of the

process heterogeneous data from the Interoperability Service module to provide optimal data to be utilized by the Energy Analytics Applications and AI Trained Models layers. The datasets coming

6.2.2 Homogenisation

Homogenisation module is to

from the Interoperability Service module will go through a data pre-processing pipeline, which contains specific micro-services for data cleansing and curation, anonymization, harmonization and transformation.

Data cleansing and curation micro-services will act to identify and remove outliers, data inconsistencies, substitute predefined values, reformatting fields and perform noise reduction.

Data anonymisation will take care to protect data sets with sensitive information by removing and deleting sensitive data, if necessary.

The data harmonization and transformation will take care to integrate data from the various sources and restructuring these under the I-ENERGY common data that will be based on already existing data model and ontologies. This process will ensure that the data processed within the Data Service layer will adhere to the same standards and to a common set of terms, concepts and relations across different data sources.

Figure 30 Figure 30 shows the high level Homogenisation module conceptual architecture:

Figure 30: Harmonisation module conceptual architecture

6.2.3 Streaming module

The Streaming module acts as gateway for the harmonised data sharing from the Homogenisation module to the I-ENERGY upper layers (Energy Analytics Applications and AI Trained Models). Specific channels/topics will be opportunely defined to share the harmonised data sets coming from the Homogenisation module. The topics definition will take into account the attributes, characteristics, type of data and origin identified during the data ingestion and harmonisation processes.

6.2.4 Data storage

The Data storage module that will be set up within the I-ENERGY ecosystem will take care of storing data that will be gathered by the Interoperability Service module and processed by the Homogenisation module. The collected data will be available for services, tools, platforms developed within the Energy Analytics Applications and AI Trained Models layers.

6.2.5 Blockchain based data sharing Model

One of the technology assets which will be leveraged on, matured and integrated withing I-ENERGY is the ENG blockchain-based multi-sided flexible marketplace. ENG has been one of the pioneers to work on DLT/blockchain and smart contracts to support both decentralized data handling and

exchange as well as decentralized marketplace to coordinate peer-to-peer energy and/or flexibility trading within a variety of H2020 projects (eDREAM, SOFIE, Coordinet, PlatONE). Such marketplace technology asset will be operated at the local grid level by any grid network operator (e.g. DSO), third party market operator, or aggregator in the case of flexibility trading and optimal aggregation, allowing any prosumer to directly participate in the market trading sessions. This is of great importance to integrate many small-scale distributed energy prosumers to exploit cooperative procurement models. The market will match consumers with energy producers and will rely on energy tokens for representing the energy as a digital asset in the energy market. It will enable controlled access to data from different sources offering a data catalogue and a discovery service to support Service Providers or Data Consumers an easy access and detection of needed data.

Energy tokens are generated at a rate proportional with the forecast energy production at the micro-grid level, transforming the energy into a transactable digital asset. The producers and consumers will then use tokens to participate in the electricity market sessions, leveraging on self-enforcing smart contracts. The digital marketplace leverages on self-enforcing smart contracts to manage, in a programmatic manner, the P2P energy trading between distributed energy prosumers (see Figure 31). During a market session, each prosumer will submit bids and offers (i.e. from their contracts) representing the amount of energy they are willing to buy or sell. The use of smart contracts will allow the participants to automatically submit bids and offers; validity checks ensure that market session rules are not violated; the evaluation is performed by the smart contracts.

Figure 31: Marketplace ecosystem

The architecture of the component and the flexibility of the model allows to extend it to capture beyond economic dynamics of energy consumers/prosumers and allow them to lay the foundations for facilitating and enabling a multi-dimensional trading off and reciprocal value compensation of energy versus data and computing resources. Hence, we envisage that the innovative maturation of ENG marketplace will incorporate innovative yet configurable multi-dimensional energy consumers preferences and incentives typologies within smart contracts and new different domains like the energy domain.

6.3 AI Trained Models Layer

The I-ENERGY Trained Models Layer is the layer where ML/DL models employed by various AI services used by applications in the upper layer (Energy Analytics Applications) are defined, trained and evaluated to confirm their performance before deployment. Thus, the layer can further be divided into the following four main components as shown in Figure 32 below:

- (i) Model Definition and Training
- (ii) Model Evaluation and Serving
- (iii) Trained Models Store
- (iv) Cross Stakeholder Transfer Learning

Figure 32: I-ENERGY Trained Models Layer

6.3.1 Model Definition and Training

The Model Definition and Training component of the I-ENERGY Trained Models Layer is the component where the task of model definition for various I-ENERGY services are carried out. It also here that effective training approach for the models taking into consideration the type of data involved, its size etc. are defined. Herein, the models could be a classification, clustering, regression models, etc.

T3.3 in WP3 focuses entirely on this component. Hence, we refer interested reader to deliverable D3.4 for more details on the requirement, proposed workflow and tools needed to realize this component. It utilizes data from the data services component to train the models and produces a trained model which is subsequently stored in the Trained Models Store as the output. Note that the data used here are the offline data. Further, when needed, the component is also used to retrain models when they degrade significantly after deployment.

6.3.2 Model Evaluation and Serving

The Model Evaluation and Serving Component uses data from the data services to evaluate already trained models stored in the Trained Models Store to ensure that it is performing as expected. This is done before the models are made available for the associated Energy Analytics Service(s) and Applications. Thus, the evaluated models are first stored in the Trained Models Store (versions) prior to their serving for the services. Also, it is the duty of this component to optimize the models for various production environments. Refer to deliverable D3.4 for more details on this component including its objective, requirement and the selected approach and tools to realize it.

6.3.3 Trained Models Store

The Trained Models Store refers to the storage resource for saving trained and evaluated models. Hence, it acts as the common storage location for the models after training, evaluation and re-training (when degradation in performance is noticed). Apache Cassandra¹⁵ database is a good candidate for this component based on its scalability, performance and fault tolerance.

6.3.4 Cross Stakeholder Transfer Learning

This component involves adaptation of already trained models for use in another domain where the available data for model training is not adequate. It could involve both intra as well as inter domain transfer learning as needed. Similarly, details about this component in terms of its need within the context of I-ENERGY, the requirements and proposed approach for its realization are elucidated in deliverable D3.4.

6.4 Application Layer - Energy Analytics Applications

The I-ENERGY Energy Analytics Applications comprise all application and microservice related components of the project namely AI models, Digital Twin Applications, User Interfaces (UIs) and I-ENERGY Marketplace. A succinct architecture diagram of Energy Analytics Applications is illustrated in Figure 26 accompanied by the relationships and interactions amongst its subcomponents.

Figure 33: Energy Analytics Applications Architecture Diagram

In a nutshell, Energy Analytics Applications heavily depend on data flows from the Data Services Layer. As illustrated in Figure 26 AI services layer consists of independent microservices that provide inference endpoints corresponding to the different I-ENERGY services that have been defined in [x] and are being developed in WP3 and WP4 based on pilot datasets. Two independent digital twin services (Distributed Energy Resources coordination and Digital Twins for Energy Consumers) receive data both from the data services layer along with predictions produced by the AI services layer and provide either grid simulations or EV-charging stations management capabilities respectively accompanied by front-end applications (UIs). Finally, the I-ENERGY

¹⁵ https://cassandra.apache.org/_/index.html

marketplace offers a set of tools dedicated for SMEs, potential innovators and developers to design and develop potential new services at scale in the field of the energy sector based on the rest of Energy Analytics Applications. The subcomponents of Energy Analytics Applications are briefly described in the following sections while provides detailed and thorough descriptions of each one of them.

6.4.1 AI Services

In the context of AlaaS this I-ENERGY layer comprises independent AI microservices. Microservices offer a modular approach and therefore can be functional either in a stand-alone setup or in conjunction with other services with minor dependencies. This flexible architecture allows for the more efficient development, extension and scaling up of the architecture based on the needs of each use case.

Either trained in an offline or online manner on the pilot datasets provided by the data services layer pilots the AI services will provide either real-time, periodic or on-demand inference according to the needs of each specific use case via inference endpoints open to the digital twin layer and pilot client services through the I-ENERGY infrastructure. The API models that are being considered for the implementation of these endpoints are REST, gRPC¹⁷ and OpenAPI¹⁸ while the Pub/Sub¹⁹ model is being investigated in terms of asynchronous communication.

The provided AI services by I-ENERGY fall in 5 broad categories:

- › Energy Forecasting (to be developed in WP4)
- › Flexibility Forecasting (to be developed in WP4)
- › Predictive Maintenance (to be developed in WP3)
- › Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (to be developed in WP3)
- › Anomaly Detection (to be developed in WP3)

Regarding the technology stack, Table 8 demonstrates the technologies that are being considered throughout the various stages of the AI service lifecycle.

Lifecycle stage	Technologies
Model Development	Python ²⁰ (scikit learn ²¹ , pytorch ²² , statsmodels ²³ , darts ²⁴ , tensorflow ²⁵ etc...), R (urca, forecast, tseries packages etc...), MLflow ²⁶ , MinIO ²⁷
Application development	Python, Flask ²⁸ , Docker ²⁹ , Kubernetes ³⁰ , Flask RESTful ³¹ , Django-rest ³² , PostgreSQL ³³
Model Serving Interoperability	BentoML, MLflow, gRPC, Apache Kafka ³⁴ , RabbitMQ ³⁵
Interconnection with AI4EU	gRPC, AI4EU Experiments ³⁶ as an extension of Acumos ³⁷ , Docker

Table 8 - Technology Lifecycle stage

6.4.2 Digital Twin Applications

6.4.2.1 Digital Twins for Distributed Energy Resources (DER) coordination

Within the scope of I-ENERGY, at the AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) level of the Energy Analytics Application, DT models for distributed energy resources (DER) provide a virtual replica of modern electrical

power systems for simulation. In addition, they incorporate a prediction layer derived from the developed and trained models of the AI Services Layer. The DT software architecture implements a modular approach by means of microservices in contrast to a monolithic software solution. Each microservice fulfills well-defined tasks that can be developed and run independently as demonstrated in Figure 26

Figure 34: System architecture of digital twin for distributed energy resources

The DER Digital Twin is composed of a simulation core (based on the DPSim³⁸ simulator) as one microservice, which will perform the simulation. A data gateway (Villasnode³⁹) handles the data traffic of the Digital Twin. It helps to integrate live and historical measurements, as well as AI services output into the simulator. Additionally, it can be used to retrieve simulation results to support further analysis in combination with other AI services. Finally, an additional component for data persistency and visualization extends the Digital Twin application with a UI.

6.4.2.2 Digital Twins for Consumers and Electrical and Thermal Communities

The Digital Twin for Consumers and Electrical and Thermal Communities enables owners of charging stations and building administrators to monitor electricity consumption of their assets in real time. Furthermore, the service allows charging station owners to remotely control the charging station hardware. The service consists of 3 main subcomponents:

- › Visualization and Monitoring element: The service receives data related to demand centres indirectly via appropriate webhooks or directly via WebSocket connection to the IoT device. Through a front-end dashboard (Visual Analytics Service explained below) building administrators and owners of charging stations can identify their assets on the map and receive information concisely through icons and colour grading that update in real time to match the status of the asset. They can quickly review data across the range of their assets through the map environment or aggregated list. Detailed information is available through asset specific dashboards.
- › Remote control and transaction clearing features: Owners of charging stations can remotely initiate, stop and authorize new charging sessions and reservations. Pricing and availability of charging stations during specific time intervals can be modified remotely by charging stations owners. Historical data can also be accessed per charging station. Data related to upcoming charging reservations in specific charging stations are also visualized in the dashboards. Troubleshooting commands to the hardware devices via the digital service such as resetting the device, unlocking the type 2 EV charging connector, etc.
- › Dynamic pricing of supplied energy: The service also draws wholesale price data in hourly intervals from Heron SA webhook. Based on these inputs, the service also proposes pricing changes to the charging station owner in hourly intervals. For example, for hourly intervals

with low wholesale energy price and low projected station occupancy, significant price reduction in cost per kWh will be proposed to the charging station owner to attract EV drivers. The technologies that are being utilised for the development of this Digital Twin application are Python Django¹⁶, React¹⁷, Redux¹⁸.

6.4.3 Visual Analytics Service

The service provides a visual dashboard relating to pilot data stemming from electricity consumption centres. Until this stage of the project, development is mainly focused on EV charging station visualisation modules while relevant communications have been established among the service and Heron SA smart meters. Specifically, the visualiser presents real time data related to electricity demand in building and EV charging stations in user friendly way. Focus is placed on spatial representation. Demand centres are represented as points on a map and user can access data through cards on the map and demand centre specific dashboards.

In terms of technology stack the Visual Analytics Engine makes use of the following:

- Python Django for the back-end
- The WebSocket protocol to establish connection between visual analytics server and the IoT energy consumption devices such as smart meters and EV charging stations.
- PostgreSQL + PostGIS database to handle special data from EV charging assets.
- NextJS for the front-end

6.4.4 Marketplace

At the PaaS level (Platform as a Service level) the I-ENERGY Marketplace will provide a virtual workbench with an easy to use and user-friendly web UI to facilitate the activities of the end user in creating new services together with a unique access point for a set of project datasets collected during the ingestion phase in the Data Services layer and a set of ML models created within the context of the project and shared to the platform thanks to the I-ENERGY ML models library.

The 2 main subcomponents of the I-ENERGY marketplace are illustrated in Figure 27 and are the following:

- › **Energy Data & Services Innovation Hub:** This tool will provide SMEs, developers and potential innovators a graphical UI to develop in scale new applications revolving around the project along with datasets and available ML models trained and produced throughout I-ENERGY.
- › **Model/Resources Selection Cockpit:** This component will contribute with a library/catalogue of reusable AI-based ML models developed within the I-ENERGY project. It will allow the selection of specific algorithms (e.g., correlation, feature extraction, ML-based classification) and the type of analytic to be executed (descriptive, predictive, prescriptive) leading to quick adaptation and reuse of ML models in different contexts.

¹⁶ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹⁷ <https://reactjs.org/>

¹⁸ <https://redux.js.org/>

Figure 35 - I-ENERGY Marketplace conceptual architecture

The core technology of the I-ENERGY Marketplace is Knowage Suite⁴³.

6.5 Security and Access Control

As security is an ever evolving process where new types of security vulnerabilities appear with the evolution of IT systems, the INERGY Security Framework defined three security planes to be periodically revisited and improved during the project’s lifetime. As depicted in Figure 36, the first plane refers to data security across all three architectural layers of the project: Data Services, Trained Models and Applications. The second plane refers to Model Security and spans the Trained Models and Applications while the third layer refers to the access to energy applications and services.

Figure 36 – INERGY Security Layers.

Table 9 summarizes the essential security guidelines followed by the INERGY framework. With respect to data security, possible attack types can consist of data breach when unintended users get access and possibly extract data, bias in and poisoning of data where a malicious entity modifies the data to determine malicious consequences up chain by manipulating the models and analytics services provided on that particular data. Such data security attacks can be prevented by having security checkpoints across the data security layer from generation, through manipulation, transition among and storage on various INERGY components and systems. Additionally, related security standards and emerging tools implementing those standards should be followed and

integrated when necessary (see also discussion in D3.4). Similar security checkpoints are anticipated for Model Security and Energy Applications as per Table and D3.1 and 3.4. More specifically, the Model Security Layer is concerned with model extraction and model swapping type of attacks, recommending checkpoints related to securing the model development, storage and serving process. The Energy Applications Security is concerned with model output theft, knowledge theft, and malicious application usage as possible attack types. As a result it recommends secure manual and programmatic service and app access through fine grained AAA while also ensuring compatibility with the AI4EU platform.

	Attack types	Security checkpoints	Related standards
Data Security	<i>Data Breach, Bias in Data, Data Poisoning</i>	Secure data transition among components, its transformation and storage	ISO/IEC CD 20547-4, ISO/IEC NP TR 24027 and ISO/IEC PD TR 24028
Model Security	<i>Model swapping, Model Extraction</i>	Secure the model development, storage and serving process	ISO/IEC PD TR 24028
Energy Applications	Steal model output, Steal knowledge, Malicious application usage	Secure manual and programmatic service and app access.	SP 800-204C

Table 9 INERGY Security Framework checkpoints.

7 Hardware requirement

The ideal requirements are interpreted in more concrete and tangible criteria that can be used to evaluate I-Energy Platform. The following table can report the result of the first quantitative analysis performed in the project's first stage.

A new deep analysis will be run during the project's second stage. It will aim at having detailed information on all hardware needed for the I-Energy Platform

Table 10 - HW I-Energy Platform Requirements

INERGY-LAYER	Service	Service description	CLOUD SERVICE	CLOUD RESOURCE DETAILS FOR CLOUD COMPUTE AND CLOUD CONTAINER COMPUTE					
				NUMBER OF CPU CORES	AMOUNT OF RAM PER CPU CORE (GB)	LOCAL DISK (GB)	NUMBER VM INSTANCES	NUMBER OF PUBLIC IP	VOLUME (GB)
DATA SERVICES	Interoperability and homogenisation (T3.2)	Installation APACHE NiFI Cluster with throughput target: 100 MB/s and 10 000 events/s	CLOUD CONTAINER COMPUTE - High-memory instance	16	32	40	3	1	500
DATA SERVICES	Streaming module (T3.2)	Installation of Confluent Kafka	CLOUD CONTAINER COMPUTE - Compute-intensive instance	16	32	40	3	1	500
DATA SERVICES	Data Storage (T3.2)	Installation MongoDB	CLOUD COMPUTE - Compute-intensive instance	8	8	40	3	1	1000
DATA SERVICES	DLT/Blockchain Hybrid data sharing (T3.1)	Blockchain based notarisation	CLOUD COMPUTE - General purpose instance	8	32	40	3	1	500
AI TRAINED MODELS	Evaluation Module (T3.5)	Service for evaluating ML/DL Models	CLOUD COMPUTE - Compute-intensive instance	8	32	40	1	1	300
AI TRAINED MODELS	Serving Framework (T3.5)	Serving framework to serve ML models	CLOUD COMPUTE - Compute-intensive instance	8	16	40	1	1	300
ENERGY ANALYTICS APPLICATION	I-ENERGY Marketplace (T4.5)	Knowage Suite customisation to provide an environment to develop small scale experiment with project' data and ML models and visualize available project' ML models	CLOUD COMPUTE - Compute-intensive instance	8	16	40	1	1	300
ENERGY ANALYTICS APPLICATION	AI Model Development	Online TSO forecasting service training; Demand response training; Flexibility Forecasting training; Other forecasting services (PV, EV, etc...) training	CLOUD COMPUTE - GPU instance	16	16	50	1	1	600
TOTAL				88	184	330	16	8	4000

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